
Anger Management in Managing Tendencies of Aggressive Behavior in Adolescents

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ABSTRACT: Aggression is behavior with the intention of hurting others. Aggressive behavior in adolescents is an action that is done intentionally to another individual resulting in physical and psychological pain. This study aims to examine one of the techniques to reduce aggression, namely anger management. This research method uses a quasi-experimental design without a control group. The unit of analysis is the tendency of aggressive behavior in adolescents while the respondents are 144 vocational high school students in Bogor. Data collection uses an inventory from Cochran.

Before the treatment, all participants were given a pre-test using the Anger Inventory . Respondents were then given training on anger management for 5 (five) times, namely 1) Grow flower Teenagers 2) Management of violent behavior 3) Assertive behavior 4) Stress management and 5) Relaxation techniques.

KEYWORDS: Adolescents, aggression, anger management

INTRODUCTION

In the social-emotional development phase of adolescents, behavior is one of the characteristics of adolescent development. The behavioral phase generally develops to meet social expectations as a form of good response in society. However, negative behavior arises because of social relationship factors that influence it. Negative behavior is not a characteristic of normal adolescent development, adolescents who develop will show positive behavior. One of the negative behaviors shown by adolescents is aggressive behavior, which is an action that is done intentionally to another individual that causes physical and psychological pain in the other individual. Aggressive behavior in adolescents is an action that is done intentionally to another individual that causes physical and psychological pain. Forms of aggressive behavior among adolescents consist of physical aggressive behavior and verbal aggressive behavior. The dominant physical aggressive behavior is hitting and throwing. Verbal aggressive behavior is generally in the form of arguing, mocking, and saying harsh words. However, the most common aggressive behavior is verbal aggressive behavior. The triggers for the emergence of aggressive behavior among adolescents internally are normative beliefs, anger and frustration. While external aggressive behavior is triggered by provocation from others, the existence of peer gangs, parents who are strict in solving a problem, and lack of communication between students and parents, as well as teachers. So that it provides a very big opportunity for students to carry out aggressive actions.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a quasi-experimental design without a control group. The unit of analysis was the tendency of aggressive behavior in adolescents, while the respondents were 144 vocational high school students in Bogor. The sample was randomly selected from the population of vocational high school adolescents in Bogor City. Respondents then filled out an anger inventory adopted from Cochran

Before the treatment, all participants were given a pre-test using the Anger Inventory . Respondents were then given training on anger management for 5 (five) times, namely 1) Grow flower Teenagers 2) Management of violent behavior 3) Assertive behavior 4) Stress management and 5) Relaxation techniques. Then a post-test was conducted

RESEARCH RESULT

Based on the results of the study, it turns out that there is no significant effect between the provision of anger management training and the tendency of aggressive behavior in respondents ($n = 144$). The results of the analysis of the provision of anger management techniques on the tendency of aggression in adolescents show that the values between the pre and post tests have the same average value (mean). From the standard deviation value during the post test, the value is greater than the pre test. So it is proven that both variables between the pre test and post test have the same value.

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Table 1. Aggressive Tendency of Pre-test Respondents

(N=144)

Mean	Median	Mode	St. Dev	P value
70.55	70	67	10,947	0.004

Table 2. Aggressive Tendency of Post-test Respondents

(N=144)

Mean	Median	Mode	St. Dev	P value
68.57	69.4	71	11,006	0.000

From the results of the study, the management of anger management in adolescents was declared meaningless. This meaninglessness is likely influenced by:

1. Predisposing factors for the tendency to be angry include biological factors related to the function of the hypothalamus, especially the frontal lobe which regulates thoughts and emotions. Psychological factors include personality, past experiences, self-concept and coping. Social factors, aggressive behavior is carried out by most people with secondary and low education.
2. Precipitation factors include biological stressors, psychological stressors and socio-cultural stressors.
3. Aggressive behavior in adolescents can also be caused by the impact of mass media. The results of Browne, Chaterine and Giacristy's (2005) research in England showed a relationship between media violence and criminal behavior. In Indonesia, several research results showed a relationship between media and violent behavior with a negative pattern, meaning that the better the media exposure, the lower the violent behavior. The same thing was also found by Badingah (1993) who stated that the fondness for watching violent films was positively related to increased aggressive behavior in adolescents.
4. The main factor that has the most influence on adolescent behavior is the family factor which can be seen from the characteristics of parenting patterns applied to children, the level of parental education, family structure and family environment.

DISCUSSION

Aggression as behavior that is intended to hurt others either physically or psychologically, where the other person does not want to be hurt. While Samuel defines aggression as behavior that causes physical or psychological injury to a person or other creature or causes damage to objects. (Brigham).

Aggression is not a consequence of behavior. However, a behavior is aggressive if there is an intention to hurt others. Aggression is divided into two, namely hostile aggression and instrumental aggression.

a. Hostile aggression is an aggressive action with the primary goal of hurting or injuring the victim. b. Instrumental aggression is aggression carried out by an organism or individual as a tool or way to achieve a certain goal. Instrumental aggression is aggressive behavior that has the primary goal of gaining access to objects, space or rights that are owned.

According to Hafiz Hidayat, et al., the form of aggressive behavior in adolescent students is in the form of physical aggressive behavior, damaging and destroying objects around them, actions taken by someone to hurt others physically such as hitting, pinching, kicking, pushing, and throwing. In addition, there is verbal aggression. Verbal aggression is aggressive behavior that appears in the form of harsh words such as cursing, arguing, shouting, insults, criticism, and other harsh words. Verbal aggressive behavior is maladaptive behavior that is not in accordance with norms or rules. 2. Triggering Factors for Aggressive Behavior in Adolescent Students internal factors and external factors. Internal factors in the form of normative beliefs. Student aggression is also caused by internal factors in the form of normative beliefs about aggression by accepting aggressive behavior as the right action. External factors in the form of Imitation and provocation Imitation is one of the factors that trigger aggression because the imitation process is a complete imitation process to anyone, be it a figure, parent, movie star and others. The next factor is provocation. Provocation Actions that cause a person's reaction such as anger or cause someone to start doing something.

CONCLUSION

Aggressive behavior can be reduced by various techniques. In this study, it was seen that Anger Management Techniques were not significantly able to reduce the tendency of aggressive actions, but must be done with other combined methods to maximize the three cognitive, psychomotor and affective aspects holistically.

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